

The Effect of Training Program on Nurses' Knowledge and Practice Regarding Control of Neonatal Nosocomial Infections in Pediatric and Obstetrics and Gynecology Teaching Hospitals, Gezira State, Sudan

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Abstract

Nosocomial infections remain a major cause of morbidity and mortality worldwide. Knowledgeable and skillful of nurses play profound role in saving neonatal life. NIs represents a universally serious health problem and a major concern for the safety of both patients and the health care providers. This quazi-experemental hospital based study was aimed to assess the effect of the training program on nurses' knowledge and practice regarding control of neonatal nosocomial infections in Pediatric and Obstetrics and Gynecology Teaching Hospitals, Gezira State, Sudan. Sixty four nurses in neonatal care units during the period from (2019-2020) were participate in this study. Data was collected using structural self-administer questionnaire and analyzed by using (SPSS) version (23). This study showed that a significantly higher increased of percentage results for all questions regarding knowledge about concept of infection, Nosocomal infection, infection control during insertion of cannula and control of Nosocomial infection in post-intervention compared pre-intervention. Nurse's knowledge regarding prevention and control of Neonatal Nosocomial infections were improved after training program especially regarding definition, causes, and source of infection. The study concluded that there is significant improvement in nurses' practice regarding Prevention and control of neonatal nosocomial infections after the implementation of the training program. The study recommended that to conducted periodic training program about prevention and control neonatal nosocomial infection.

Introduction

Nosocomial infections (NIs), also known as a hospital-acquired infection, are defined as infections which are acquired after 48th of patient admission. Such infections are neither present nor incubating prior to a patient's admission to a given hospital. NIs represents a universally serious health problem and a major concern for the safety of both patients and the health care providers [1]. With the exception of Group B streptococcal or Herpes simplex virus infection, is usually hospital acquired, particularly in infants who are hospitalized from birth. These infections are associated with increased mortality rates, immediate and long term morbidity, prolonged hospital stay and

increased cost of care [2]. Nosocomial or hospital acquired infections threaten the survival and neurodevelopmental outcomes of infants admitted to the neonatal intensive care unit, and increase cost of care. Premature infants are particularly vulnerable since they often undergo invasive procedures and are dependent on central catheters to deliver nutrition and on ventilators for respiratory support [3]. Prevention of nosocomial infection is a critical patient safety imperative, and invariably requires a multidisciplinary approach. There is no short cuts hand hygiene before and after patient contact is the most important measure, and yet, compliance with this simple measure can be unsatisfactory. Alcohol based hand sanitizer is

More Information

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effective against many microorganisms and is efficient, compared to plain or antiseptic containing soaps [4]. The use of maternal breast milk is another inexpensive and simple measure to reduce infection rates. Infection prevention and control is urgent. Nurses are in a key position to disseminate knowledge and practice through health education and providing proper nursing care resulting in prevention and control of neonatal nosocomial infections and decrease mortality and morbidity of neonate [5]. Outbreaks of NI have been related to overcrowding, understaffing, and contamination of equipment, environment, medications, and even breast milk [6]. 86% of nosocomial pneumonia is associated with ventilation. Fever, leucopenia, and bronchial sounds are common symptoms of VAP Nosocomial infection in very low birth weight (VLBW) infants is a common complication with high morbidity. New strategies to reduce its occurrence have recently led to the development of neonatal surveillance programs [7].

Materials and Methods

Ethical Consideration

Permission from managers and matrons of Wad Medani Pediatric and obstetrics and gynecology Hospitals was made through official letters and verbal acceptance was obtained from them date 31-03-2019.

Study Design

This is quasi-experimental (pre-post interventional) hospital-based study.

Study Area

This study was conducted at Wad Medani Town, capital of Gezira State. It is located on the Western East of the Blue Nile and about 186 km South of Khartoum. It is located in Gezira Scheme which is the largest agricultural project in Sudan.

Sample Size

The numbers of nurse were sixty four participate in the study.

Study Duration

The study started from 2019 up to 2020.

Inclusion Criteria

All the current registered pediatric nurses who work at the pediatric and obstetrics and Gynecology teaching hospital in neonatal unit.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Nurses who are working in other Departments of the Hospital.
2. Nurses under training.

Data Collection Tools

Data was collected using two tools:

Tool 1: Structural self-administered questionnaire was designed by the researcher and translated to Arabic language it included two parts:

Part one: Including demographic characteristics such as: age, level of education, years of experience, training course, marital status, need for learn about standard precision and department.

Part two: Nurses; knowledge about NCI prevention and control such as: assessment of standard precautions, 8 questions.

Tool 2: Standardized Observational checklist include: observation of resources, using PPE, hand washing, cleaning and disinfectant of environment and equipment, management of waste.

Phases of Intervention

Pre intervention phase is a pilot study was done on a sample of seven nurses in an effort to test the validity and feasibility of the questionnaire instrument. Before the training program a questionnaire was distributed for each available nurse to fill it within (45 – 60) minutes.

Program Implementation

The program was designed to equip the nurses with essential information and practice regarding care of neonatal infants with nosocomial infections, and immunization of children to improve their knowledge and practice measures to prevent and control nosocomial infections when caring of the neonate infants. The program was implemented in three days and every day three sessions done to, twenty tow nurses in each day. All the participants were attended the sessions and participated actively in practical sessions. The practical training continues for two months, done to six groups. A post-test was made using a questionnaire, to evaluate the effect of program on nurses' knowledge regarding neonatal infants with nosocomial infections nursing care.

Data Analysis

The data were coded, entered, and analyzed using the statistical package for social science (SPSS) version (23), the p value less than 0.001 significantly difference.

Results and Discussion

The data were coded, entered, and analyzed using the statistical package for social science (SPSS) version (23), the p value less than 0.001 significantly difference.

The results of pre-intervention and post-intervention knowledge regarding infection control presented significantly high increased percentage in post intervention which ranged between (79% to 59%), compared to pre-intervention which ranged (17% to 36%) Table-1.

Table 1: Results of Nurse Knowledge Regarding Concept of Infection for Pre and Post Intervention

Terms	Pre - intervention						Post- intervention						P.Value
	Good		Satisfaction		Poor		Good		Satisfaction		Poor		
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
Definition of infection	11	17%	5	9%	50	78%	44	69%	8	13%	12	19%	.000
Mood of transmittion include	23	36%	13	20%	28	44%	38	59%	14	22%	13	19%	.015
Sources of infection	20	31%	9	14%	35	55%	45	79%	12	18%	8	12%	.000
Percussion for prevent infection	30	47%	16	25%	18	28%	41	64%	12	19%	11	17%	.044
Total	20	31%	11	17%	33	52%	42	63%	8	13%	12	19%	.010

This study showed that (8%) of study participants their performance were adequate about infection control measure and (92%) their performance were inadequate about infection control measure that were differed from study done by Aliaga S, *et al.*, [8].

The results of pre and post intervention knowledge about concept definition nosocomial infection (NCI) in the post-intervention presented the percentage for

good questions were increased which presented range of percentage between (59% to 70%) compared to good in pre-intervention (17% to 48%) and also for satisfaction in post-intervention were increased which presented (13% to 22%) compared to pre-intervention which presented in range between (3% to 23%) Table-2.

Table 2: Results of Nurse Knowledge Regarding Nosocomial Infection for Pre and Post Intervention

	Pre - intervention						Post- intervention						P.value
	Good		Satisfaction		Poor		Good		Satisfaction		Poor		
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
Definition of NCI	11	17%	2	3%	51	80%	39	60%	9	15%	16	25%	.000
Factors that increase the NCI in the unit	11	17%	7	%	46	%	44	69%	8	13%	12	19%	.000
Causes of NCI in hospital	23	36%	15	23%	26	41%	38	59%	14	22%	13	19%	.000
Health provider and standard percussion	31	48%	9	14%	24	38%	40	70%	14	9%	6	21%	.000
Total	19	29%	8	13%	37	58%	40	70%	11	17%	12	19%	.000

This study showed that a significantly higher level of knowledge was revealed in the post-intervention phase as compared with the pre-intervention phase with regards to the concept of Nosocomial infection (29% vs 70%) Table-2 these results in agreement study conducted by Yasmine S and, Galal ,1 [9], whom stated that there were significantly higher level of knowledge was revealed in the post-intervention phase as compared with the pre-intervention phase with regards to the types of nosocomial infections (94.4 vs. 76.8%). The results of post innervation percentage for good and satisfaction were increased compared to same question in pre-intervention. The results of percentage were ranged between (65% to 71%) for good questions in post-intervention compared to (33% to 44%) for

good in pre-intervention. These results similar to study conducted by Youssria E.*et al* [7], whom stated that it was adequate in 68.7% of the nurses and inadequate in 31.3%. The percentages of improvement of some items of infection control measures after implementation of the education program. The results of nurse knowledge regarding control Neonatal Nosocomial infection were increased only for good question the percentage range between (41% to 70%) in post-intervention compared to pre-intervention which were (14 % to 39%), but for poor questions were decreased range (11 % to 19%) in post-intervention compared to pre- intervention which were the percentage ranged between (78% to 50%) for poor question Table-4.

Table 3: Results of Nurse Knowledge Regarding Infection Control during Insertion of Cannula for Pre and Post Intervention

	Pre - intervention						Post- intervention						P.Value
	Good		Satisfaction		Poor		Good		Satisfaction		Poor		
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
Disinfection during inset of cannula	28	44%	7	11%	29	45%	45	71%	14	22%	5	7%	.040
Frequency for changing cannula	21	33%	5	8%	38	59%	44	69%	8	13%	12	19%	011
Signs of infection in cannula site	27	42%	11	17%	26	41%	35	56%	13	20%	16	24%	038
Total	25	39%	8	13%	31	48%	41	64%	12	19%	19	30%	036

Table 4: Results of Nurse Knowledge Regarding Control of Neonatal Nosocomial Infections for Pre and Post Intervention

Terms	Pre - intervention			Post - intervention			P.value
	Good	Satisfaction	Poor	Good	Satisfaction	Poor	
Concept of infection	31%	17%	52%	63%	13%	19%	043
Concept of Nosocomial infection	29%	13%	58%	70%	17%	19%	039
Disinfectant and sterilization	30%	13%	58%	41%	10%	135	.045
Hand washing	17%	9%	78%	69%	13%	19%	007
personal protective equipment's	%39	12%	48%	64%	25%	11%	050
Infection control during insertion of cannula	39%	19%	48%	64%	13%	39%	050
Needle disposable	27%	17%	63%	63%	17%	21%	.035
Nursing care of neonate	37%	18%	45%	59%	20%	22%	048
Neonatal fluid and nursing care in incubator	14%	11%	80%	64%	32%	11%	001
Neonate nutrition and fluid	28%	14%	50%	66%	17%	17%	038
Total	25%	13%	62%	63%	18%	19	035

Conclusion

Nurse's knowledge regarding prevention and control of Neonatal Nosocomial Infections improved after training program especially regarding definition, causes, and source of infection. There is significant improvement in nurses' practice regarding prevention and control of neonatal nosocomial infections after the implementation of the training program.

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Conflict of Interests

Authors declare no conflict of interest.

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